

FARMER FIELD SCHOOL ON TARO: Bridge The Gap Between RESEARCH And FARMER PRACTICES

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OVERVIEW

This paper reported a successful approach of FFS on taro (*Colocasia esculenta*) model farm conducted at Sabak Bernam, Selangor. Taro, also known as 'keladi', is cultivated by smallholders or farmers for its edible corms.

METHODOLOGY

SIGNIFICANT FINDINGS

- FFS MODEL FARM: Taro farm owned by Mr. Azli Salleh located at Kampung Parit 10, Ban Kenal Pasir Panjang, Sekinchan, Selangor.
- 20 FARMERS have participated in the FFS comprising 13 males and seven females.
- TWO TARO VARIETIES were introduced, namely 'keladi wangi' and 'keladi putih'.
- TWO TYPES ACTIVITY: Main activity and group dynamic activity.
- SPECIAL TOPICS related to taro cultivation addressed technical issues or other topics important to taro cultivation were shared with farmers.
- THE KNOWLEDGE AND LESSONS shared with the farmers were very well accepted.
- THE SIZE AND THE PHYSICAL APPEARANCE OF THE CORMS (1-2 kg per corm with conical shape) can be sold at RM3 per kg.

ECONOMY IMPACT

- Promotion of new types of varieties: **KELADI WANGI** and **KELADI PUTIH**. An alternative to keladi mawar sold commonly in the market.
- INCREASE PRODUCTION** of keladi in the local market.
- ADOPTION OF GOOD AGRICULTURE PRACTICES** in taro cultivation

SOCIAL IMPACT

- STRENGTHEN THE FARMER'S COMMUNITY WITH LOCAL AGENCIES:** group meeting/discussion.
- EMANCIPATION OF WOMEN:** promote equal participation, breaking sexual customs related to gender roles.

CONTRIBUTION TO MYS/SDG

Sustainable Development Goals of 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development
National Food Security Policy Action Plan 2021-2025 of MALAYSIA

FARMER FIELD SCHOOL ON TARO @ PASIR PANJANG, SABAK BERNAM, SELANGOR

01 AGRONOMY & BOTANY

02 PEST & DISEASE MANAGEMENT

03 BIODIVERSITY & CONSERVATION

04 COMMUNITY SEEDBANK

05 FARMER'S RIGHTS

06 POST HARVEST MANAGEMENT

07 TARO PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

